

careables.org

Deliverable 3.3

Platform v3 and Documentation tool with Open Standard and Certification

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The objective of this deliverable is to illustrate, with a non-technical approach, the final structure of the Careables platform, which is about co-design in the healthcare domain and gathers documented solutions helping people with disabilities perform a task, with an improvement of the quality of their life. We call these open solutions “careables” emphasizing their ability to take care of people’s health.

In the third phase of *WP3 Platform & Tooling*, co-design and emerging needs of the maker communities - especially connected to the COVID-19 response - guided the creation of new features and both architectural design and contents decisions, and this improved platform functionality, usability, and user experience.

The platform has two constituting instances - which are closely interconnected but can be also accessed individually - and have the following distinctive functions:

- the Careables website (www.careables.org) is the main point of entrance for our users (makers, healthcare professionals and people with disabilities) and provides knowledge and support towards self-activation;
- the Welder website (www.welder.app/careables) is the repository of careables and an environment for collaborative development using the documentation tool.

As to the open standard for documentation, the Careables team has joined the discussion with Open Know-How, a group of open hardware organisations and individuals working on the topic. The first version of the Open Know-How Standard was released late in 2019: it is an additional file or manifest, which is machine-readable and contains project metadata and references to the documentation. As in the third year we focused more on enabling collaboration and dissemination of knowledge - urged also by the COVID-19 pandemic - rather than on portability, we have decided to implement the Open Know-How Standard in the next future as long as it is supportive for our diverse communities.

The deliverable has the following structure: first, it presents background information, objectives, and methodology behind the platform development, and illustrates the implemented features and designs concerning COVID-19 maker response. Then, it continues with the description of careables.org, namely its design process that informed the latest release and its main aspects. The third chapter is dedicated to the updates and new features of [Welder.app](http://welder.app), including the documentation tool.

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List of abbreviations

AH	Agile Heap
API	Application Programming Interface
CD	Continuous Deployment
CE	Conformité Européenne (European health & safety product label)
CI	Continuous Integration
CR	Care recipient
GIG	Global Innovation Gathering
HP	Healthcare professional
KUL	KU Leuven
LP	Lead partner
OPEN	OpenDot
TOG	Together to Go Foundation
WAAG	WAAG society
WEV	Wevolver
WP	Workpackage
ZSI	Centre for Social Innovation

1. Introduction

The Careables platform is a living online environment that supports a wide community of makers, designers, healthcare professionals, and people with special needs or physical limitations in (a) acquiring knowledge and know-how on digital fabrication and design for care, (b) developing and (c) sharing open solutions that improve autonomy and social inclusion. As resulted from the initial research and benchmark and following development carried out in *WP3 Platform & Tooling*, the Careables platform is composed of two instances:

- careables.org, that introduces visitors to the concept of open hardware in healthcare and guides them towards information based on their background, interests, and needs;
- welder.app, which is the repository of documented co-created solutions for disabilities and hosts the documentation tool.

This final document is descriptive and provides an overview of platform development over the third year, while impact considerations are in deliverable *D4.3 Final Impact Assessment Report incl. Impact Assessment Package* and dissemination, awareness, and outreach activities through the platform are reported in *D5.4 Final Dissemination and Sustainability Report*. It is addressed to those interested in collaborative platforms and practises of user-centred design and consists of three sections as follows:

- Section 1 presents the methodology, summarizes the objectives, and briefly explains the contribution against the COVID-19 outbreak;
- Section 2 focuses on the careables.org system, the design process, and the new functionalities and sections that emerged after the user-feedback collection;
- Section 3 regards Welder.app implementation and the newly added features.

1.1. BACKGROUND

(1) The Careables approach is based on co-design: multidisciplinary teams of people with various skills and experiences - doctors, therapists, nurses, makers, designers, caregivers, and patients - collaborate together and come up with a new effective, and personalized solution for disability. Therefore, users are not objects of study but are actively involved, supplying insights about tacit knowledge, real needs, and personal values, taking part in the concept development and evaluating the proposed solution, as also well synthesized in the Manifesto of Co-design for Health and Care by OpenDot¹.

(2) Careables is part of the wide ecosystem of actors and social, sometimes informal, participatory projects that have been innovating the healthcare system from the bottom-up, putting patients and their caregivers at the center of the process with positive impacts on their quality of life. But what are enabling factors that trigger

¹ The Manifesto is available here: [link](#) [Accessed: December 17th 2020]

patient activation and, more generally, willingness and ability to change for better health and care? Surely, digital transformation represents a powerful driver because it has opened up alternative systems for communicating and collaborating, for producing objects easily by means of technologies like 3D printers, and for sharing designs openly. Careables platform is set into this context.

(3) The main target groups of Careables platform are heterogeneous:

- people with disabilities and their carers;
- healthcare professionals;
- designers, engineers, makers;
- stakeholders dealing with social innovation programmes (ie. public entities, universities, foundations).

Through the findings we gathered while engaging with the target groups in our multiple activities, we observed that people have different technology and e-health literacy that builds motivations, capacities, and confidence, and consequently are at different levels of innovation readiness. This applies to all our target groups without distinction.

(4) Although (a) co-design as a practise has entered pioneering health and care centers, training, and learning institutions, (b) an increasing number of makerspaces and fab labs deal with healthcare and co-design, and (c) patient-driven innovation enables people with disabilities to take care of their own health, it is important to provide some guidance for potential adopters and channel their proactivity through an access point. To such purpose, the Careables platform is a virtual space born to increase the capacity building of both individuals and organisations in response of disability-related needs utilizing both cross-sectoral learnings to acquire skills and competencies, and new ways of networking and sharing knowledge and solutions.

1.2. ITERATIVE AND COLLABORATIVE PROCESS

WP3 is led by OpenDot, overseeing its whole carrying out against objectives, tasks, and milestones, while the platform implementation is the result of a mix of technical competences and experience, and defines a division of roles with a significant degree of autonomy as follows:

- OpenDot is responsible for the design, development, iteration, and testing of Careables.org;
- Wevolver tasks regard the implementation of Welder.app, the open-source website which includes the documentation tool.

The following timeline visually summarizes the implementation status of the platform as described in previous Deliverable 3.1 and Deliverable 3.2:

Figure 1: Timeline

What the timeline doesn't show is the continuous and dynamic process behind it, which allows any improvements of the platform, especially those regarding usability and content optimization. We have applied the *spiral design* methodology, which implies an iterating cycle of activities leading to a prototype (the platform) which is tested with real users, to understand its weaknesses, and eventually redesigned, starting from the gathered insights.

Figure 2: Spiral design

Over the Careables project lifetime, the implementation of WP3 has seen the participation of the whole consortium, not only to achieve timely and successfully the overall goals but also to take advantage of specific research competence and skills, as well of the close cooperation through the prescribed co-design approach. Besides, WP3 has run in parallel with the other WPs, integrating their outputs and contributions and this is reflected also in the architecture of the platform as detailed in the images below:

WP1	WP2	WP4	WP5	WP6
Engagement & Community Growth	Pilot Open Solutions	Evaluation & impact assessment	Dissemination & Outreach	Legal & Ethical Aspects
LP: WAAG Contributions: open calls, solutions, toolkit, community map	LP: AH Contributions: open healthcare map, taxonomy, solutions	LP: ZSI Contributions: user tests and platform impact analysis	LP: GIG Contributions: contents ie. events, events reports, stories	LP: KUL Contributions: guidelines for documentation tool and platform

Figure 3 and 4: Connection with other WPs

1.3. OBJECTIVES

The third phase of WP3 has the following objectives:

- to test the platform observing how people navigate it;
- to collect feedback about the platform from healthcare professionals and people with disabilities, the two target groups that are less familiar with collaborative platforms and making for health&care;
- to implement the platform's interface and user experience, resolving priority issues that emerged from user-testing and coming up with a smooth user flow;
- to turn careables.org into a learning hub about digital fabrication technologies applied to health&care and co-design methodology;
- to improve the documentation tool, shifting towards an open standard for documentation;

- to make the open-source repository and documentation tool available to other communities and organisations;
- to close the final version of the platform.

1.4. CAREABLES AGAINST COVID-19

The screenshot shows a webpage section for COVID-19. At the top left is a circular image of a woman wearing a face shield and a white surgical mask, with her hand raised in a gesture. To the right of the image is the heading "COVID-19 Together we care!" followed by a paragraph of text and a "READ MORE" button. Below this are two white boxes with orange borders. The left box is titled "Careables for COVID-19" and contains a short paragraph and an "EXPLORE CAREABLES" button. The right box is titled "Resources for COVID-19" and contains a short paragraph and an "EXPLORE TOOLS" button.

Figure 5: Careables.org homepage - COVID-19 section

The COVID-19 crisis has turned the spotlight on the maker movement and online communities volunteering for good, on open hardware and DIY solutions for health&care, on local community-based production, and open-source design. Since the outbreak of coronavirus in Europe - and Italy was the epicentre - the quick mobilization of makers has proven the importance of acting collaboratively and sharing knowledge, and in that sense, reinforced the Careables proposition. Then, we updated our plan for WP3 to commit to COVID-19 response through the platform. The following table briefly details the activities we put in place:

Table 1: Overview

Careables against COVID-19	
Careables.org / new contents	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• updated homepage with COVID-19 section• COVID-19 extra page• updated "Find careables" page with a new category, namely <i>careables for COVID-19</i>• new COVID-19 related stories and tools

Welder.app / new contents

- updated homepage with COVID-19 button
- addition of special tags to describe COVID-19 projects (such as “face shields”)
- extra collection of COVID-19 projects
- curated selection of COVID-19 careables

Connection with other platforms

- partnership with Tech for care² and Make in Italy³
- deploy of the listing feature linked to Welder.app

² Tech for Care link: [here](#). [Accessed: December 18th 2020]

³ Make in Italy link: [here](#). [Accessed: December 18th 2020]

2. Careables.org

Figure 6: FI-CO, a careable co-designed during the Health&Care Summer School 2019

Careables.org acts as a welcoming environment that introduces healthcare professionals, makers, designers, and people with disabilities to the paradigm of open hardware for health and care, explaining challenging or new information and concepts, like digital fabrication and co-design and providing to them actionable knowledge, skills, and tools that can improve their personal or professional life. We started from a problem that exists, that of the limitations of commercial aids for people with disabilities, and have created a platform that can help that lively ecosystem - not only made of individuals but also organisations worldwide - to emerge, thrive, establish connections and work better.

Technically, Careables.org is built on WordPress with a tailor-made theme and is the result of:

- the research phase with the baseline mapping of existing collaborative platforms⁴;
- the information we gathered through user-fields tests, surveys, and interviews to outline the profiles of our potential users;
- the new definition of careables.org objectives - to inspire and to get involved - after the co-design session held in Milan in February 2019;

⁴ *Accessibility Awesome List*, an ongoing open list of platforms by OPEN: [link](#). [Accessed: December 22th 2020]

- the feedback of our target groups during the user-tests;
- the iterative design and development process shaping the structure, interface, and layout.

2.1. DESIGN PROCESS

Figure 7: Timeline

After the second release of Careables.org last October 2019, the third-year implemented activities focus on getting the effectiveness of the overall platform under the microscope, as to understand whether it is:

- useful, because it provides adequate answers to people's real - and not perceived - needs and enables them to accomplish their goals;
- usable, because it delivers a fulfilling user experience in terms of content and visual aspects.

Following a user-oriented approach, we involved healthcare professionals, makers, designers, and people in search of a solution and their carers, to inform further significant improvements of the platform and corrected course, in order to get to its final version hereby presented.

Also, user-testing doesn't represent a validation of work done but rather it questions assumptions and allows us to grasp functional but also social design aspects to incorporate in the platform, with regard, for example, to visual identity and image selection. And beyond technical requirements, development issues, and user-interface fine-tuning, this iterative process has given us the chance once more

to get in close contact with our target groups, learn through empathy and see their enthusiastic reactions when they discover careables.

This is a detailed description of all the activities carried out stated in the above timeline:

1. First user test feedback analysis: Between November and December 2019, ZSI led a first user test regarding the platform (Careables.org and Wevolver.app) that involved potential users in structured interviews. The results were shared during the consortium meeting in Wien of 12-13 December 2019 and then elaborated through cluster analysis in January. Homepage emerged to be the critical point.

2. Platform fixing, redesign, and implementation: Following the first user-test, some major issues and bugs were fixed in February, in collaboration with ZSI that contributed to a revised mock-up for the homepage. The fixed issues implied a rearrangement of homepage grid-structure, improved texts, and different showcases of contents block. However, this quick fine-tuning affected the overall vision and narrative behind the Careables project and the design consistency. Consequently, a new redesign was needed. During the online consortium meeting of 19-20 March 2020, we shared the redesign proposal that was then implemented within May.

3. Careables.org against COVID-19: Being a project dealing with health and care, as the COVID-19 pandemic was evolving rapidly, we immediately decided to address the emergency and prevention. To such purpose, we selected and shared both open source solutions developed by makers and healthcare professionals worldwide and useful materials and sources, and we told stories coming from the Careables community, ie. in Brazil and the Netherlands. The COVID-19-related contents appear in *Homepage*, *Discover Careables*, *Resources*, and *Stories* pages and are visually distinguished by orange-color for title, background, navigation interactions, and borders.

4. 3rd Careables release: The new version tackled the issues that emerged during the first user test and the main changes were a new headline on top of the homepage, a new extra page about co-design methodology ("*See how it works*"), integration of Twitter feed in homepage, stronger visual elements including videos, new menu links, and items ordered, clearer texts, wording and proposition (ie. the definition of what careables are).

5. 2nd user-test organisation: Between May and June 2020, we worked on a new user-test with the objectives of not only checking the latest platform iteration but also understanding of the platform inspires people and helps them integrate the Careables approach and mentality in their daily life. With the help of Prototypes, we structured a 1 to 1 remote interview of no more than 1 hour, which consisted in 3 tasks (defining participatory design, finding careables, searching the careables team) and follow-up open questions; also it was declined for two categories of users: healthcare professionals and care recipients. A folder containing guidance, HP and

CR presentations, HP and CR data-recording google forms were provided to all partners.

6. 2nd user-test and feedback analysis: together with TOG we involved 7 healthcare professionals and 4 care recipients in the qualitative user-testing to verify requirements. Each session foresaw the presence of a facilitator, who guided the interview, and an observer, whose role was taking notes of participant's behaviour and comments. By performing the tasks, successfully or partially, participants provided feedback about usability, wording and language, visual elements, platform effectiveness, and their satisfaction. The insights were collected live using a google form and then elaborated by our user-experience designer.

7. Platform implementation: the in-depth analysis of user-test results guided the re-design and implementation. In general, the evaluation of participants was positive about platform layout, user flow, and contents, while main priority issues regarded clarity of language, usage objectives, and, again, the cognitive load needed to fully digest what careables are and how they are created, compared to the commercial aids our target groups are accustomed to.

8. 4th Careables.org release: the new platform maintains the same structure and graphic design (ie. colour palette and layout) but refines the tricky wording (ie. from *Discover Careables* to *Find Careables*, from *Resources* to *Tools*), introduces a new feature, namely the search bar, re-articulates the *Contact* page, providing partner profiles, and reduces the complexity of designer/maker lexicon.

9. Careables.org for the Glifo Kickstarter campaign: with the launch of the Kickstarter campaign for Glifo, the writing tool for children with physical impairments, we added a special and interactive pop-up box (for desktop and mobile) to inform careables visitors and direct them to the official crowdfunding page.

10. Community map and final fixing: our user-testing proved the necessity of creating a link between potential users and organisations like fab labs that can support the development of customized careables. The community map (included also in deliverable 1.3) shows the wide ecosystems of actors that deal with health and care.

2.2. FINAL VERSION OF CAREABLES.ORG

Figure 8: Careables.org final homepage

The outcome of the previous design process is the final version of Careables.org, whose useful, usable, and engaging structure is outlined as follows:

Homepage: the landing page opens with a static headline followed by a short paragraph, summarizing the platform scope, who are the key actors involved, what they do together and what careables are, with a supporting image from the Open Health HACKademy. The link “See how it works” opens up an extra page which eventually explains in practise the overall participatory approach. Then, the concept of “careables” is reinforced, introducing the use of digital fabrication technologies and the disability domain.

After the COVID-19 section and the specific tool-boxes, there is a series of featured careables (*careables for COVID-19*, *careables we-codesigned*, and *careables for fun and leisure*), whose transition from a careable to another can be also controlled by the user.

As the careables approach is unusual and rather disrupting, reaffirming the importance of person-centred care, the platform also invites to explore a set of tools (*Welcome mix*), explicitly collected for each target group, to answer their doubts (ie. *Why do I need design?*), acquire skills and knowledge and become activators. The closing call-to-action is followed by social media feeds, newsletter subscriptions, and highlights from the *News&events* page.

Figure 9: Final platform architecture

Then, as illustrated above, Careables.org sections are:

COVID-19: it presents both the Careables contribution during the COVID-19 pandemic in terms of information sharing and the guiding principles for making safe and useful open hardware in health and care.

About: it tells the project background and the mission and reiterates possible novel concepts for new-comers like digital fabrication technologies. This section contains the *Community map* explanation and link.

Find careables: it incorporates the careables taxonomy (deliverable 2.1), with the extra COVID-19 category, and invites to explore the collection on Welder.app or to add new careables.

Tools: it shares interesting resources filtered by 6 categories (*Principles, Methodology, Training Kit, Certification&Legal, Careables-How-To, Deliverables*), in connection also with other EU projects, and their goal is to help our target groups - a person with disability namely *I have a healthcare need*, healthcare professional namely *I am a Healthcare professional* and designer/maker namely *I like tinkering - gain knowledge, awareness, and skills*.

Stories: as people are at the center of the careables approach, this page gives voice to their direct experience in making careables through curated content so that other users can identify and empathize with them and see new opportunities.

Contact: it details each partner's key expertise to address specific user problems, doubts, or requests.

News&Events: it showcases news and events, both from the consortium partners, and other relevant organizations working in design for care.

Also, the following figure summarizes the evolution of careables.org visual identity: from a technology platform (ie. almost muted color palette but the light blue logo, innovation-centric photography, maker language) to a welcoming and fresh platform, communicating encompassment and sense of novelty (vibrant colors, people-centric images, simplified language for healthcare professionals and people with disability).

Figure 10: Careables.org chronological evolution

The table outlines the updated and distinctive features of the final version of Careables.org:

Table 2: Overview of Careables.org

Careables.org	
Users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● people with disabilities and their carers; ● healthcare professionals; ● designers, engineers, makers.

What users can do

- understand what participatory design means
- browse careables starting from the taxonomy
- read published stories and see compelling videos
- achieve knowledge and information to dive into the careables approach
- get started making careables
- upload existing careables or just co-created careables
- take part in events or join the careables community locally
- use the search functionality

Key-aspects

Specificity: the platform is about careables, tailor-made solutions that suit patients' needs and improve the quality of their life and are created thanks to digital fabrication technology to allow their replicability.

Co-design methodology: diverse and sometimes-unheard experiences and skills bring different perspectives and understandings and have driven the implementation of the platform.

Openness: it is the principle implied in the maker movement and the platform guarantees free access to contents and documentation.

Change-making culture: innovation is not by default because it breaks long-established norms, but the platform provides evidence-based solutions (*careables*) and practises (*Tools*) that help redefine the system we are living in.

Collaboration: there is a distributed ecosystem of organisations that have been working on health and care, and the COVID-19 maker response has shown how impactful it can be. The community map keeps a trace of the valuable connections we set.

Engagement: Careables project acts through both the offline local communities co-creating solutions and the online community around the platform.

Capacity-building: Careables approach is based on human capital and the platform empowers people to think outside-the-box and make the most of their

	<p>expertise.</p> <p>Cross-sectorial learning: the platform provides knowledge - ie. that of makers in digital fabrication technologies or that of healthcare professionals who are familiar with aids categorization of our taxonomy - and fosters individual upskilling.</p> <p>Empathy: as emerged also during the Careables meet-up, a positive feeling is created when people listen to each other. The stories we collected and told through the platform make people open to new experiences and differences.</p>
Technical features	<p>Usability: the online environment (mobile/desktop) is conceived to be user-friendly, facilitating the user-experience and articulating the Careables approach visually.</p> <p>Accessibility: the online environment is conceived to be widely accessible and easy to use. This is done both on the code of the website (proper HTML definition, optimized responsiveness, avoidance of dependency on external libraries) and the thoughtful style choices for graphic components, texts, and templating.</p> <p>Deployment: Simplified architecture, redefinition of sections, tailored WordPress theme and custom plug-ins, modern and adaptive CI/CD and testing through hosted git repository.</p>

3. Welder.app

3.1 TIMEFRAME FOR 2020

The following table shows the main activities regarding Wevolver.app implementation and their timeframe:

Table 3: Overview

	From	To
Deployed a search engine that enables users to find any project on the platform	January	March
Enabled people to find extensive info about open hardware licenses, and a link to a tool to choose licenses during the project creation process	February	February
Created a page to showcase COVID-19 solutions	March	March
Updated our tagging system to make it easier for Careables moderators to feature content, and an extended list of available tags	May	July
Created a feature that enables people to create lists of projects, as well as allow developers to embed these lists on external websites using RSS.	August	November
General bug fixing and performance maintenance	January	December

3.2 WELDER NEW FUNCTIONALITIES

This is a complete list of the implemented functionalities over the third year of the Careables project:

Search engine

Previously, in order to look for specific projects on the platform, people used to

browse the Featured Careables page or select a taxonomy category/tag. To make the process easier, we deployed the search functionality: using the search bar people can now find projects based on any search term they enter.

The search engine makes use of Google's search algorithm. That means that projects are retrieved and ranked as Google would do. Also, we've personalized the displaying of the relevant information from the search results on top of this, to ensure the results show the title of the project correctly, as well as a banner image.

Info about open hardware licenses

Figure 11: Documentation tool - licences fields

How to properly license a project is an unfamiliar notion for many users, so information and support at the stage of documenting are fundamental. At the same time, this is an opportunity for users to learn more, and for the consortium to explain the importance of open source.

During the project creation process, as well as when editing project settings at a later stage, users can now find an extra page with detailed information about open hardware licenses and how to select a license for their project.

How does the licensing system work?

The application of a copyright license on a work is possible as a subsequent phase followed by the initial acquisition of copyright protection. In other words, the author first automatically obtains the copyright for his/her work and then he/she decides on how to regulate his/her exclusive rights by applying a license on such work whose effects are spread on variety of indeterminate subjects.

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CERN OHL v1.2

Through this CERN Open Hardware License ("CERN OHL") version 1.2, CERN wishes to provide a tool to foster collaboration and sharing among hardware designers. The CERN OHL is copyright CERN. Anyone is welcome to use the CERN OHL, in unmodified form only, for the distribution of their own Open Hardware designs. Any other right is reserved. Release of hardware designs under the CERN OHL does not constitute an endorsement of the licensor or its designs nor does it imply any involvement by CERN in the development of such designs.

TAPR OHL

The TAPR Open Hardware License is TAPR's contribution to the community of Open Hardware developers. TAPR grants permission for anyone to use the OHL as the license for their hardware project, provided only that it is used in unaltered form.

Figure 12: license explanation

Updated tag system

We learned that the way to tag projects and to display all projects in the Featured Careables page (<https://www.welder.app/careables>) of the Welder.app was cumbersome and caused confusion among the Careables moderators, whose role is assigned to consortium partners. Therefore, we added an extra feature that directly enables moderators to choose the projects that will be featured via the user interface.

This change proved to be useful also to rearrange and complete new project's tagging, improving the chances for a user to find what he/she is looking for.

COVID-19 page

Figure 13: COVID-19 page on Welder.app

At the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, we realised that many people started creating and sharing open source solutions, ranging from 3D printable face shields to complex ventilator systems. As Careables consortium, we curated and selected projects either tested or designed within the consortium, or only from a reliable source/organisation. We aggregated these solutions on the platform using tags and we displayed them in the collection of COVID-19 projects.

Analytics showed the growth of visits and interactions on the platform, parallel to the diffusion of the pandemic. Even if it happened in an emergency context, it proved the importance of projects for health and care, and platforms to collect and organize them.

Listing feature

Early on in the pandemic, maker initiatives in Italy had sprung up intending to gather information about solutions, which tackled the shortage of medical supplies, such as masks, ventilators, etc. We collaborated with two different Italian platforms, namely Tech for Care (www.techforcare.com) and Make in Italy (www.makeinitaly.org), whose need was to display a number of projects that were hosted on Welder. Since sharing projects externally made them spread on a wider scale and to a larger user base, we realized that there was a big opportunity in developing a feature that would make this process easier, providing centralized documentation systems, as well as flexible interaction and integration within independently designed platforms.

In order to support the dissemination of emergency solutions for hospitals and “meet the communities at their place”, we leverage on the Welder.app and its open source codebase, so that these websites could use Welder’s API to extract the required information from the platform. However, the way to select projects to be displayed externally was limited and complex.

To solve this problem, we developed the feature which enables anyone to create lists of projects under their own account; secondly, we provide a RSS link that allows external parties to access these lists and display them on external websites.

Analytics from that period of COVID-19 outbreak shows a traffic growth from Italy because this feature has been tested and used by Tech for Care and Make in Italy.

Figure 14: traffic growth during COVID outbreak

Dispositivi

Home » Dispositivi

I DISPOSITIVI qui presentati non sono certificati e potrebbero presentare delle controindicazioni oppure non funzionare adeguatamente. Si raccomanda, per chi volesse utilizzare la documentazione per replicarlo, di avvalersi della collaborazione di personale tecnico specializzato per la realizzazione e della supervisione di un medico per l'utilizzo. E' assolutamente sconsigliato replicarlo se privi di tali competenze ed in ogni caso sempre e solo in mancanza di altre alternative.

Novel Transparent Face Mask

A novel transparent face mask was designed and

Aerosol Box

A transparent acrylic box, to avoid contamination of healthcare professionals by secretion

Surgical Mask Strap

A remixed strap version to ease the tension of surgical masks over the ears

The screenshot shows the Tech For Care website interface. At the top, there are logos for Maker Faire, Tech For Care, and I-RIM. Below the logos is a navigation menu with items: HOME, INIZIATIVE, NEEDS, SOLUZIONI, IMPLEMENTATIONS, TEAM, ITALIANO. The main content area features a large red banner with a virus-like pattern and the text: "Tech For Care is the open platform for sharing emergency resources and projects COVID - 19". Below this is a paragraph of text explaining the platform's purpose. A "Slide" section contains three cards: "I have a need" (with a person icon), "I have a solution" (with a lightbulb icon), and "I can Build and Realize" (with a gear icon). At the bottom, there are logos for various partners including careables, LAB, CNP, and MEDAARCH.

Figures 15 and 16: external platforms using Welder.app API to display Careables projects

3.3 CERTIFICATION

Over the project duration, we worked trying to understand how to incorporate certification into the documentation tool, considering aspects such as who are the users making careables, what are the careables, people with disability safety, and safe careables.

We discovered that:

(1) The research carried out in WP6 made clear that Careables users shall individually consider whether they should be considered as ‘manufacturers’ according to the EU law (see D6.1 and D6.2). If they qualify as such, they shall carry out a conformity assessment for the products they aim to put into the market. Also, they shall evaluate the possibility of undergoing a certification procedure, in order to obtain a CE marking for the product being manufactured. However, in many cases, users of the Careables platform will be individuals replicating objects in their household activities, where different and lower degrees of due diligence will be required. Thus, in this second case, going through certification processes is likely to be not necessary. Furthermore, the Careables.org platform is not primarily responsible for suggesting applicable standards to its users.

(2) Beyond the legal requirements, we explored the certification of medical devices and its applicability to careables with researchers from the EU Ubora project⁵ and Tech for care partner and again we found out that:

- careables are custom-made solutions created/co-created by individuals with different background (and usually not manufacturers, to which a specific EU regulation is applied);
- most of the careables don't fall in the category of medical devices and the rest are usually within the lower safety classes;
- if careables are not medical devices, it is enough that creators inform people about possible risks when using the solution and document properly;
- if careables are medical devices that belong to class 1, creators can start a self-assessment procedure and check the compliance with the general safety requirements and harmonised standards.

(3) Also, we gained some practical lesson learned from the maker response to the COVID-19 pandemic:

- some careables can obtain certification as medical devices like the case of the *Prousa face-shield*⁶, while other careables are classified as “extra protection” like the *Intubation box*⁷ but used in hospitals and emergency settings;
- the *Charlotte valve*⁸ is a 3D printed plastic valve used in respiratory ventilators and, according to the European Commission, it “may qualify as either accessory of medical devices or their parts and components.”
- The *Charlotte valve* can be printed with standard 3D machinery and makers, fab labs, private printer owners and companies offered to print it to help hospitals suffering from shortages of ventilator masks. But, even if documentation is properly done with all the specifications and requirements, in some cases the safety and quality assessment is simply a matter of testing in the field. In this specific case, many 3-printed Charlotte valves were discarded when they were tested in the hospitals. The reasons were due to necessary

⁵ The UBORA platform: [link](#) [Accessed: January 11th 2021]

⁶ Prousa face-shield on Welder.app: [link](#) [Accessed: January 11th 2021]

⁷ Intubation-box projects on Welder.app: [link](#) [Accessed: January 11th 2021]

⁸ The Charlotte valve used in Easy Covid 19 project: [link](#) [Accessed: January 11th 2021]

technical features: the mechanical strength and flexibility of the snap, together with the precise fit to guarantee an airtight assembly. These problems were solved in two different ways, without improving the documentation. In details:

- A. **the problem does not exist:** if properly printed with a machine of good quality and reliability, the valves worked and neither improvement of documentation or extra information were needed;
- B. **the original design of the valve doesn't render or doesn't give good results with the machines used:** different open source alternative designs emerged in parallel with printing frustrations. New improved designs and following new documentations were openly shared.

Based on these findings we conclude that:

- it is important to disseminate within the maker community basic knowledge about certification processes to understand better when it is needed and how to proceed and we provide insights and practical resources like the *Open Source Medical Devices – A visual Guide for Makers* developed by the DSI4EU project into the Tools section;
- cooperation with existing projects, such as UBORA, is the best way to answer the need for guaranteeing the safety of the careables;
- documenting runs in parallel with prototype ideation and design and flexibility is required to avoid barriers to the participation of users,
- imagining an alternative way to “peer review” and “approve” the careables could increase the confusion on the topic of certification and doesn't prove to be effective as demonstrated by the Makers Making Change platform;
- at the moment, an easier and equally safe alternative to certification is hard to imagine and implement.

Following these findings and considerations, we have updated the Terms and Conditions of Welder and address users to our *Tools* to learn more about certification.

With this said, it is fundamental to work on more agile certification processes to support decentralized validation, along with decentralized production. In prospective, it is possible to imagine solutions, emerging in parallel with the evolution of both fabrication technologies and maker communities.

3.4 DOCUMENTATION TOOL FUNCTIONALITY

Table 4: Overview of Welder.app functionality

Types	Feature
Account & user profile creations	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Create an account (including user name)● Add profile photo● Add profile text, website link, and social media links

Project creation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add project thumbnail • Add project title, description, tags, • Add a license, and learn more about licenses • Set project to public or private
Project overview documentation creation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add images and video to a media gallery • Write a summary about the project (including images and video) • Write a text describing the goal the project tries to achieve (including images and video) • Add specifications (a table with attributes such as size, power usage, etc. that describe the project) • Write a text describing the roadmap of the project (including images and video) • Write a text describing the team (including images and video) • Add references (a table to describe the reference and add links to the external source) <p><i>Note: everything can be edited by the project creators.</i></p>
Project documentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add files of any type, including a message to describe the update • Create a new folder to add files in • Create and edit in the browser a text page, which will be stored in the project as an openly accessible and downloadable file • Preview commonly used files such as 3D files in the browser • Download files that were uploaded by project creators
Project documentation, Assembly guide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create, edit, and reorder an assembly guide that contains steps, consisting of 1) images or videos, 2) a bullet-pointed text to describe how to build the project • Download an html file of the assembly guide
Project revision management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • View the history of each file, and as a project creator be able to restore a previous version (without losing newer iterations) • View the history of the whole project; being able to instantly change every file of a project to a historical state and inspect a project as if it were at such a historical date
Comment on projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leave comments, and reply to other's comments • As a project creator, get a notification when people comment on your work

Browsing	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• View related projects with similar tags• View an overview of all Careables projects• View an overview of all Careables projects in a sub-category• View all projects with a certain tag
Searching	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Search all content on the platform for any specific term used
Following	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Follow a project and receive email notifications when a project gets updated or when people make comments
Listing	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Create lists with a collection of selected project, add or remove projects to this list• Receive an RSS link for each list that enables to embed the selection of projects on external websites
Desktop client	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Install a program on your desktop computer that enables the synchronisation of all files of a project with a folder on your local computer

3 tutorials for appropriate use, documentation, and sharing are available in the *Tools* sections of Careables.org and are:

- *Documenting Careables projects on Welder*, a step-by-step video by Wevolver⁹;
- *How to create a project on Welder*, a pdf file by Opendot (Annex 1);
- *How to edit a project on Welder*, a pdf file by Opendot (Annex 2).

3.5 OPEN STANDARD

At the start of the project, the Careables consortium intended to implement an open standard for documentation, to simplify interactions and cooperation among different platforms.

In parallel, the Open Know-How team¹⁰ started working on developing a similar standard in 2019 and we have established an ongoing collaboration: Wevolver and Careables are listed in the strategic partners¹¹.

The objective of the Open Know-How Standard is to disseminate “better designs created by all, shared with all. Step-by-step, industry-standard open hardware recipes to recreate, build on, or adapt as required” (source: openknowhow.org).

This means that all the projects that adapt open know-how standards should be:

- *Discoverable*: Instant instructions to make anything as, when and where

⁹ The video is available here: [link](#) [Accessed: December 29th 2020]

¹⁰ Open Know-How website: [link](#) [Accessed: December 29th 2020]

¹¹ Open Know-How Participants page: [link](#) [Accessed: December 29th 2020]

needed. Search for open hardware, regardless of where it resides.

- *Portable*: Documents publishable in multiple formats. Cohesive data standards that are easy to use, freeing up time to make more things and help more people.
- *Interactive*: Write once, circulate everywhere. Faster publishing with maximum reach, speeding up research and reproduction.

A first version of the Open Know-How Standard was released late in August 2019 and can be accessed on the related website. It is conceived as an additional file or manifest, which is machine readable and contains project metadata and references to the documentation.

We eventually decided not to proceed in working on a standard for documentation following these evaluations:

- open standard should be a “commons”, collaboratively and inclusively designed and broadly used by existing and future communities;
- Careables is part of Open Know-How together with partners with very specific expertise and competencies. We can achieve something we wouldn't be able to achieve by ourselves;
- developing a new open standard - working independently from the Open Know-How group - would be inefficient and ineffective.
- our tool developed to support documentation is helping to get homogeneous output and is easily understandable also to non-experts, such as people with disabilities and healthcare professionals;
- adopting the Open Know-How Standard for existing documented careables would mean producing an extra file with metadata for each project, involving the users in the process and we learned that documentation is rather problematic, especially for those new to the topic;
- adoption of the Open Know-How standard could be done at any moment.

Also, the Open Know-How standard is currently in its “version 1”. The working group continues to evolve the standard based on received feedback and some dimensions like modularity and interoperability remain open issues to consider, as also reported in the recent research *Standardisation of practices in Open Source Hardware*¹². We will continue following the developments of the Open Know-How group and consider the possibility to implement the standard as a feature at a later stage.

As to continue the fruitful collaboration between the Careables project and the Open Know-How group, a resource about Open Know-How Standard will be prepared and added in the *Tools* section of careables.org.

¹² The research *Standardisation of practices in Open Source Hardware* by Jérémy Bonvoisin, Jenny Molloy, Martin Hauer, Tobias Wenzel, can be accessed here: [link](#).

4. Conclusions

Within the Careables project, the main objective of WP3 was to design a collaborative platform in the domain of disabilities and populate it with open healthcare source solutions, that means that are created with digital fabrication technologies and are documented to enable replication and adaptation on user's needs.

The Careables platform originated from the experiences of Opendot and Wevolver, in close collaboration with the whole consortium. This led the process of research and design to the final Careables platform which provides:

- a knowledge base in form of inspiring tools and stories about co-designing open healthcare solutions for disabilities so that people can navigate novelty, learn, engage with their own situations, and put acquired skills and competencies into practice;
- an easy documentation tool and a lively repository of concrete and replicable solutions.

Also, we deepen our understanding of key facilitating aspects:

- **Know the specific challenges** - Careables was born to answer the mis-match between specific and unique needs/problems of people with disabilities and devices that are meant to assist them in performing a particular task and we propose an appropriate, effective, needed, and achievable approach - that of online collaboration, sharing knowledge and open healthcare hardware;
- **Learn from others** - Careables platform took shape in a growing landscape of organisations dealing with tech and social innovations like the pioneering D4E1 - Design For Everyone initiative by Howest University or Makers Making Change platform - listing Careables in its resources - and enlarging our network increased our capacity with regards especially to technical and common issues like ie. open standard or documentation for diverse target groups.
- **Design is a participatory process** - Careables platform is the outcome of a rounded perspective, involving healthcare professionals, people with disabilities, and makers and it has benefitted from this process.

ANNEX

Annex 1: How to create a project on Welder by Opendot

Annex 2: How to edit a project on Welder by Opendot

WELDER.APP

How to create a project

by Antonio Garosi

Welder.app

Let nothing stop you from innovating

- Better organization of your project's files; always one clear latest revision.
- Review & retrieve any past moment in time, with unlimited project-wide revision history.
- Trace back past decisions and considerations using annotated revisions.

For private & public projects

- Join thousands of hardware developers contributing to open source hardware projects from around the world, or develop proprietary technologies with selected team members in private.

[VIEW PROJECTS](#)

Careables.org repository is hosted by Welder.app, a file sharing and version management solution, empowering both private teams and open communities.

<https://www.welder.app/>

Careables Org

Platform for open healthcare solutions.

About

[EDIT](#)

Careables is an open and inclusive approach to healthcare for citizens based on digital fabrication, distributed manufacturing and collaborative making.

<https://www.careables.org/>

My Projects

[CREATE A NEW PROJECT](#)

Crutches Pads

With Crutches Pads is possible to walk on sand with a normal crutches.

Braille Keyboard Covers Keys

Silicone keys to allow blind people to use keyboard.

[MORE](#)

Create a project - Access

Browse Careables.org and click on the **Discover careables** section

In the opened page, click on the **Upload My Project** button

Create a project - Profile

If you already don't have one, you'll be asked to activate a Welder account and to log in

From the hamburger menu on the upper-right corner, click on the profile section

In the "My Projects" section, click the "Create a new project" button to access to the Project Upload Wizard.

Step 1

Project Settings

Thumbnail *

Title *

60 / 60

Description: Pitch your project in 90 characters or less. *

90 / 90

Tags: Categorize your project to make it easy to find.

| v

License: Choose what rights you grant others to copy, distribute, or modify your work.

| v

Privacy

- Public**
Anyone can see this project. You choose who can modify it.
- Private**
You choose who can see and modify this project.

Step 1 - Thumbnail

Project Settings

Thumbnail *

Upload Image
At least 800x500 pixels

Title *
60 / 60

Description: Pitch your project in 90 characters or less. *
90 / 90

Tags: Categorize your project to make it easy to find. ?
 | v

License: Choose what rights you grant others to copy, distribute, or modify your work.
 | v

Privacy
 Public
Anyone can see this project. You choose who can modify it.
 Private
You choose who can see and modify this project.

The **Thumbnail** will be the main picture of your project. It should be a clear and well-defined image, since it will be used to showcase your project on Welders and Careables.

Choose an image big at least 800*500 pixels, preferably oriented in horizontal.

This is a mandatory field! You can't save your project until you upload a Thumbnail Image.

Step 1 - Title & Description

Project Settings

Thumbnail *

Title *

 60 / 60

Description: Pitch your project in 90 characters or less. *

 90 / 90

Tags: Categorize your project to make it easy to find. ⓘ

 | v

License: Choose what rights you grant others to copy, distribute, or modify your work.

 | v

Privacy

- Public**
Anyone can see this project. You choose who can modify it.
- Private**
You choose who can see and modify this project.

Insert the project **Title** and a brief **Description** of it.

Keep the description concise (90 characters max) since it will be used just to have a first glance of your project content. You'll have plenty of space later to delve into details.

These are mandatory fields! You can't save your project until you prompted them.

Step 1 - Tags, Licence & Privacy

Project Settings

Thumbnail *

Title *

Glifo 55 / 60

Description: Pitch your project in 90 characters or less. *

Glifo is a tools which ables kids suffering from disabilities to express their creativity 1 / 90

Tags: Categorize your project to make it easy to find. ⓘ

Select... | v

License: Choose what rights you grant others to copy, distribute, or modify your work.

Select... | v

Privacy

- Public**
Anyone can see this project. You choose who can modify it.
- Private**
You choose who can see and modify this project.

Tags are used to classify the topics of your project. Pick the most appropriate from the list prompted to make you project more discoverable to interested users. You can assign 5 tags max.

As for the **License**, The Open Hardware Licenses provided grant the the legal basis to share freely your projects. Research about them and choose the most suitable to your project philosophy (long story short: opt for TAPR if you want your idea to be used as is, opt CERN if you want share without compromising your IP).

At the moment, Welder free accounts can only set the privacy setting of the projects as **Public**.

Keep in mind that you can change all the fields of your project in later steps, so don't worry about using drafts or placeholders.

Step 2

Create Project

Step 2/2

Project Overview

Media Gallery

IMAGES

YOUTUBE

CHOOSE IMAGES

Summary: What is the product? *

B *I* ☰ ☱ 🔗 🖼️

Type something

Goal: What does this project aim to accomplish

B *I* ☰ ☱ 🔗 🖼️

Type something

Specifications: what attributes describe the product?

ADD SPECIFICATION

Roadmap: What future work is planned?

B *I* ☰ ☱ 🔗 🖼️

Type something

Team: Who worked on this project?

B *I* ☰ ☱ 🔗 🖼️

Type something

References: What external sources provide additional information?

ADD REFERENCE

Step 2 - Media Gallery

Create Project

Step 2/2

Project Overview

Media Gallery

IMAGES

YOUTUBE

CHOOSE IMAGES

Summary: What is the product? *

B *I* ☰ ☷ 🔗 🖼️

Type something

The Media Gallery is the section you can use to add more pictures of your projects. There are no size restrictions and you can add as many images as you want.

Furthermore, if you press the “YouTube” button, you can embed YouTube clips to your Media Gallery by inserting the relative link.

YouTube URL

ADD TO GALLERY

Step 2 - Summary

Project Overview

Media Gallery

IMAGES YOUTUBE

CHOOSE IMAGES

Summary: What is the product? *

B *I*

asd

In the Summary section you can describe your project in more detail. In here you answer to question such as:

- What is your product?
- How is it made?
- What's the inspiration behind it?

This field also allows you to format you text, add links and other images with the embedded commands.

This is the only mandatory field of this step. You won't be able to save your project until you fill it.

Step 2 - Goal, Roadmap & Team

Goal: What does this project aim to accomplish

B I

Type something

Specifications: what attributes describe the product?

ADD SPECIFICATION

Roadmap: What future work is planned?

B I

Type something

Team: Who worked on this project?

B I

Type something

References: What external sources provide additional information?

ADD REFERENCE

There are three more text fields that will guide in describing properly your project.

In Goal, you can describe who is the target of your product and how you aim to solve its needs.

Roadmap is where you define the foreseen evolution of your project. How will you promote it? Will you scale the production? Do you expect contribution from other people?

In Team you can list the people and the institutions that collaborated to the creation of the project in so far.

Step 2 - Specifications

Goal: What does this project aim to accomplish

B I

Type something

Specifications: what attributes describe the product?

ADD SPECIFICATION

Roadmap: What future work is planned?

B I

Type something

Team: Who worked on this project?

B I

Type something

References: What external sources provide additional information?

ADD REFERENCE

If you want to describe some physical specifications of your project (size, power consumption, range, etc), you can use the standardized form provided by pressing this button.

Be sure to define properly the unit of measurements (don't confuse internationals and imperials!) and add the units as precise as you can.

Specifications: what attributes describe the product?

	Description	Metric	Units	
ADD SPECIFICATION				

Step 2 - References

Goal: What does this project aim to accomplish

B *I* ☰ ☰ 🔗 🖼️

Type something

Specifications: what attributes describe the product?

ADD SPECIFICATION

Roadmap: What future work is planned?

B *I* ☰ ☰ 🔗 🖼️

Type something

Team: Who worked on this project?

B *I* ☰ ☰ 🔗 🖼️

Type something

References: What external sources provide additional information?

ADD REFERENCE

In a similar fashion, you can add references and inspirations of your project from this button.

A standard form will help add names, links and other useful details.

References: What external sources provide additional information?

Title 200 / 200

Link 200 / 200

Description 300 / 300

Author(s) or name of external website 200 / 200

ADD REFERENCE

Step 2 - Create

In filling the forms, try to be concise, clear and precise and make so that the media you want to show will be easy to understand.

However, remember that all the fields of a project can be edited later from your profile, so making early mistakes and doing later corrections shouldn't be your concern.

Whenever you're ready, press the **Create** button at the end of Step 2 and the project will be readily shown on your profile.

WELDER.APP

Edit a project

by Antonio Garosi

Edit Project – Project Board

The screenshot shows the Careables Org website interface. On the left, there is an 'About' section with a blue 'EDIT' button. The main content area is titled 'My Projects' and features a yellow 'CREATE A NEW PROJECT' button. Below this, two project cards are visible: 'Hands free suitcase puller- life hack' and 'Hackcess Handy Holder'. A blue 'MORE' button is located at the bottom right of the 'My Projects' section.

Careables Org
Platform for open healthcare solutions.

About [EDIT](#)

Careables is an open and inclusive approach to healthcare for citizens based on digital fabrication, distributed manufacturing and collaborative making.

<https://www.careables.org/>

[Instagram](#) [Facebook](#) [Twitter](#)

My Projects

[CREATE A NEW PROJECT](#)

Hands free suitcase puller- life hack
"Suitcase puller-life hack" leaves your hands free so no more pulling the suitcase

Hackcess Handy Holder
Attachment for holding a cup of coffee on the wheelchair

[MORE](#)

After creating a project, you can edit it and add more specifications to it.

In your Profile page you can access to your project board, where you can edit all the project you're involved in. Click on the project title to open its edit page.

Project Page

The screenshot shows a project page for 'Glifo test'. At the top left, the project name 'Glifo test' is displayed. Below it are three tabs: '3d Printing', 'Healthcare', and 'Therapy'. To the right of the project name are three buttons: '0' (with a cloud icon), 'CLONE', and 'PROJECT HISTORY' (with a gear icon). The version 'CERN OHL v.1.2' is shown in the top right corner. Below the project name is a blue link for 'Overview'. The main content area is split into two columns. The left column is mostly empty with a yellow '+' button. The right column contains a yellow 'EDIT' button at the top, followed by a 'Summary' section with the text: 'Glifo is composed by different tools which able kids suffering from disabilities to express their creativity. This has been reached through 3d printed objects that let them draw and write easily and freely.' Below the summary is a 'Team' section with the text: 'The project has been realized for TOG foundation (Milan), which takes care of these kids, in collaboration with the italian fablab Opendot (Milan).'

The browser will present you with an overview of the basic information you provided in the creation of the project.

From here you customize all the projects settings (with the yellow **Edit** button) and add more material to describe your project.

General Functionalities

The screenshot shows a project page for "Glifo test". At the top left, there are tags for "3d Printing", "Healthcare", and "Therapy". Below these is an "Overview" link. In the upper right corner, a red box highlights a set of blue buttons: a speech bubble icon with "0", "CLONE", "PROJECT HISTORY", and a cog icon for settings. Below the buttons, the version "CERN OHL v.1.1.2" is displayed. The main content area is split into two columns. The left column has a yellow "+" button. The right column has a yellow "EDIT" button. The right column contains a "Summary" section with text about Glifo being composed of different tools for kids with disabilities, and a "Team" section with text about the project being realized for TOG foundation (Milan) in collaboration with the Italian fablab Opendot (Milan).

The set of blue buttons in the upper right corner provides a set of global functionalities for the project.

These are:

- **Project settings** (the cog icon);
- **Project history**;
- **Clone repository**;
- **Questions & feedbacks** (the comic balloon icon);

General Functionalities – Project Settings

The screenshot shows the 'Project Settings' window with the 'GENERAL' tab selected. The window contains the following elements:

- Picture:** A placeholder image showing a person's hands using a blue 3D-printed tool (Glifo) to hold a yellow pencil.
- Tags:** A field with three 'x' icons and a dropdown arrow.
- Title *:** A text input field containing 'Glifo test'.
- Description:** A text area containing 'Glifo is a tool which ables kids suffering from disabilities to express their creativity' with a '2 / 90' character count.
- License:** A dropdown menu showing 'CERN OHL v.1.2'.
- Privacy Settings:** Two radio buttons: 'Public' (selected) and 'Private'.
 - Public:** Anyone can see this project. You choose who can modify it.
 - Private:** You choose who can see and modify this project.
- Buttons:** A blue 'DELETE PROJECT' button and a grey 'SAVE' button.

The **Project settings** button will prompt you a window displaying the options you provided in the Step 1 of the Create Project process. From here you can change them, or even irreversibly delete your project if you want to start the documentation from scratch.

The **Members** button will give access to the tab where you can invite other Welder members to you project, allowing them to modify the documentation.

The screenshot shows the 'Project Settings' window with the 'MEMBERS' tab selected. The window contains the following elements:

- Navigation:** 'GENERAL' and 'MEMBERS' tabs.
- Organization:** A logo for 'careables.org' and the text 'Careables Org'.
- Buttons:** A yellow 'INVITE' button and a blue 'ADMIN' button with a close icon.

General Functionalities – Project History

The screenshot shows a 'Project History' window with a table of commit messages. The table has three columns: Author, Message, and Date. The messages include actions like 'deleted files', 'uploading guide', and 'Project created'. A pagination control at the bottom shows '< 1 >'. The window has a close button in the top right corner.

Author	Message	Date
hi@careables.org	deleted files 1 changed file	2019-06-03
hi@careables.org	deleted files 1 changed file	2019-06-03
hi@careables.org	uploading guide 1 changed file	2019-06-03
hi@careables.org	Uploaded files. 1 changed file	2019-06-03
hi@careables.org	uploading guide 1 changed file	2019-06-03
Wevolver	Project created	2019-06-03

In the **Project history** you can see all the changes that were committed to the project page since its creation. This is very useful in the case of a large team working on the same project.

General Functionalities – Clone and Questions & Feedback

The **Clone** button will make you download the full repository of the project on your computer through the **Welder app**.

Questions & Feedback will take you to the comments left by other Welder members to your project, so that you can reply and interact with them.

File Tree

The file tree panel is where you can add more content to your project. In here you can add files, assembly guide and all the content that you consider relevant to your project divided in a directory tree of your preference.

Clicking on the + button will give the option of adding a **File** or a **Folder**, or an **Assembly Guide**.

Add File/Folder

Adding files to your project is rather straight-forward. Choose them via the navigation window or just drag & drop them to add them to your repository.

By pressing the **Create New Folder** button you can set and create the folder where the file will end in your file tree, but due to the version control system's internal functioning you cannot create a folder without a content. Always add a file if you want to create a folder.

Add File/Folder – Preview

After you added your files, they will appear in the file tree. Welder will also preview certain compatible file extensions such as *PNG*, *JPG*, *SVG*, *PDF* and *STL*.

The set of blue buttons in the file preview will let you copy a link to it, check the file history, download it or delete it. Remember that a folder cannot exist without a file. If you delete the only file inside a folder this will remove it as well.

Add File/Folder

Folder Name

 Overview

Files:

✓ Folde1

✓ Folder2

 3.png

266 kB

 Assembly Guide

114 B

When you add a new folder, you can also create nested folders by using a slash symbol to separate the folders.

This will significantly speed up the process of creating many folders in a project, but remember that folders can exist with a file inside of them. If you have a many nested folders relying only on a file at the bottom of the structure, deleting that file will remove the whole stack.

Assembly Guide

The screenshot shows a modal window titled "Edit Step 1" with a close button (X) in the top right corner. The interface includes a "Step Name" label and a text input field containing the placeholder text "what is this step about?". Below the input field are two buttons: "IMAGES" and "VIDEO". A large dashed border represents the main content area, which contains a blue "Upload Image" button and the text "At least 800x500 pixels". To the right of this area is a bullet point followed by a dashed box containing the text "Insert bullet point here.". At the bottom of the content area, there are three smaller "Upload Image" buttons. At the bottom left of the modal is a blue "DELETE" button, and at the bottom right is a yellow "SAVE" button.

An **Assembly Guide** is an instructional text where you describe step-by-step how to obtain a the desired result of your project (being it the whole project or just a stage).

If you want to create an assembly guide in your file tree, you'll be presented a template to add the content of your first step. You can insert the step title, images & video links for exposing the passages involved, and a bullet point list.

Assembly Guide - Bullet points

- First
- Second
 - First of second
 - Second of second

B *I*

Type something

0/350

ADD

The bullet point list features formatting and linking capabilities. Furthermore you can set the indentation level in order to create sub-lists.

Assembly Guide - Preview

After saving the first step of the assembly guide, you'll see it in the file tree preview, where you can add further steps or edit the previous ones.

You can have different assembly guides in your project - which is very useful especially for large project with many sub-systems - but you can't have two assembly guides in the same folder. Navigate through your file tree and choose the proper directory for every assembly guide you want to make.

Assembly Guide – Guide Info

Edit Assembly Guide Info [Close]

Difficulty
Select... [Dropdown]

Hours Required
[Text Input]

Components

Name	Link	Quantity
[Text Input] 50 / 50	[Text Input] 50 / 50	[Text Input] 50 / 50

[ADD COMPONENT]

Tools and Fabrication Machines

Name	Link
[Text Input] 50 / 50	[Text Input] 50 / 50

[ADD TOOL/FABRICATION MACHINE]

[SAVE]

Clicking the **Edit Guide Info** yellow button in the assembly guide preview will let you insert more information not specific to a step.

Difficulty and **Hours Required** is where you suggest a skill-level and approximate time required to complete this assembly.

Add Components and **Add Tool/Fabrication Machine** fields can be used to define materials and tools that are best suited for your project's realization.

Putting some effort in these sections will greatly improve your documentation and ensure the least amount of misunderstandings. Anyone trying to replicate your project is surely interested about what you used on what.